

INTERVIEWEES DETAIL

ID	Location	Gender	Age (y.o.)	Ethnic group	Pendidikan Terakhir	No. of family members	Years of farming experience	Farmland area (in Ha)	Farmland ownership status	Main commodity
I1	Kalampangan	Male	40	Jawa	Senior high school	3	21	0.25	Owned	Horticulture
I2	Kalampangan	Female	39	Dayak	Primary school	4	10	0.06	N/A	Horticulture
I3	Kalampangan	Male	58	Jawa	Senior high school	2	58	2.75	Owned	Horticulture
I4	Tangkiling	Male	37	Jawa	Junior high school	3	7	1.5	Rented	Horticulture
I5	Kalampangan	Female	49	Jawa	Junior high school	4	5	0.25	Owned	Horticulture
I6	Kalampangan	Male	47	Jawa	Senior high school	4	26	1	Owned	Horticulture
I7	Kalampangan	Male	57	Jawa	Senior high school	4	N/A	1 Ha	Owned	Horticulture
I8	Kalampangan	Female	53	Jawa	Senior high school	3	5	0.185 Ha	Owned	Horticulture
I9	Kalampangan	Female	50	Jawa	Bachelor degree	2	25	0.025 Ha	Owned	Horticulture
I10	Kalampangan	Male	51	Jawa	Bachelor degree	4	4	1 Ha	Owned	Horticulture, food crops
I11	Kalampangan	Female	28	Jawa	Senior high school	4	8	0.015 Ha	Owned	Horticulture
I12	Tangkiling	Male	53	Jawa	Junior high school	4	4	0.4	Owned	Horticulture
I13	Tangkiling	Male	47	Jawa	Primary school	3	31	0.75	Owned	Horticulture, food crops
I14	Tangkiling	Female	60	Jawa	Primary school	5	20	1	Owned	Horticulture
I15	Tangkiling	Male	32	Jawa	Senior high school	3	4	0.1	Rented	Horticulture
I16	Tangkiling	Female	48	Toraja	Senior high school	4	25	0.02	Owned	Horticulture, food crops
I17	Tangkiling	Female	55	Dayak	Senior high school	5	11	0.03	Owned	Horticulture
I18	Tangkiling	Female	52	Jawa	Primary school	4	4	0.5	Owned & Rented	Horticulture, food crops
I19	Tangkiling	Female	47	Dayak	Senior high school	6	7	0.5	Owned	Horticulture
I20	Tangkiling	Male	48	Jawa	Junior high school	1	40	18 Ha	Owned & Rented	Horticulture